

The Challenges Facing Tertiary Institutions in Implementing Resilient Agricultural Practices in The Matabeleland Region

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ABSTRACT

The research on resilient agriculture practices employed a multi-methodological approach, which incorporated questionnaires and observational methods. Both qualitative and quantitative methods of data collection were used. Literature was extensively interrogated on the subject. The research study revealed that climatic changes exacerbated food shortages, droughts, increased food prices, altered seasons, increased livestock death, and high incidences of pests and diseases. The adoption of Pfumvudza/Intwasa, planting of drought-tolerant crops, diversification, and early planting were among the adopted practices, yet some institutions lagged on water harvesting technologies, green housing practices, drip irrigation methodologies, agroforestry practices, and small stock production and management. Challenges inhibiting full adoption include the limitations on available land sizes, lack of mechanization, poor water harvesting facilities, lack of capital, diverse preferences by administrators on investments, bureaucratic procurement systems, and restrictive policy environments. As a measure to reduce the negative effects of climatic occurrences, tertiary institutions ought to adopt the use of fully fledged greenhouses, embrace the wide breadth of precision agricultural practices, improve water harvesting technologies and also invest in drip irrigation systems. Institutions should further expand on the growing of drought-tolerant varieties, keeping drought-tolerant small stock, and commercialize agriculture through engagement with private partnerships for funding opportunities. Employees and students need to be trained on the impact of climate change and possible resilient practices for adoption and their importance

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Definition of key terms: Climate-resilient agriculture (CRA) is a sustainable approach for converting and reorienting agricultural systems to support food security under the new realities of climate change through different types of adaptation and mitigation mechanisms (Debangshi, 2021).

Resilience is the ability of a system and its components to anticipate, absorb, accommodate, and recover from any negativities faced (Debangshi, 2021).

Climate change:

Tertiary institutions:

INTRODUCTION

Zimbabwe, an agro-based economy with most of the rural populace heavily relying on agriculture for survival, faces the negative impacts of climate change. Incidents associated with climatic changes resulting from global warming have resulted in the resurgence of several natural calamities that have claimed both human beings and animals. Droughts, heatwaves, pests and disease outbreaks, flash floods after heavy cyclones and hailstorms have been on the rise in recent years posing a significant threat to both agricultural productivity and human life (Sinath, Rejitha and Lokesh, 2024, CIAT, 2017). Institutions of higher and tertiary education, though regarded as the powerhouses to drive innovations for the sustenance of humanity and economic development of the country, have been highly vulnerable to the effects of these climatic changes. Adoption of various resilient agricultural practices has been seen as a tool to effectively deal with the advent of the negative effects of climate change. It is against the challenges brought up by these climatic changes that the research study on the impacts of resilient agricultural practices has been undertaken.

BACKGROUND INFORMATION

Natural disasters pose a significant threat to agricultural productivity globally (Sinath, Rejitha, and Lokesh, 2024). The challenge has seen a rising number of people worldwide, regionally, and in Zimbabwe facing food insecurity (CIAT, 2017). Whilst agriculture is practiced as livelihood by the citizens in most communal and urban areas, it is also threatened by these natural disasters. Its importance as a major source of employment, both formal and informal sectors, agriculture accounts for nearly 13.3% of Zimbabwe's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The recent projection that Eastern and Southern regions of Zimbabwe will continue to experience even drier conditions shows the magnitude of the food insecurities problem and stimulates debate on coming up with robust, resilient practices (Worldbank, 2021). It is against this background that proper implementation of large-scale climate resilient practices is seen as an alternative strategy in reducing vulnerability and high risks associated with climate change (Rahaman *et al*, 2018). Tertiary institutions, also regarded as the main powerhouses to drive innovations for the sustenance of humanity and economic development, are handicapped in implementing adequate resilient programmes (Vincent *et al*, 2023).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The ever-changing climatic conditions have seen the resurgence of some environmental negativities that include droughts, changes in seasonal rainfall patterns, and temperature extremes, which have seen most farmers losing large tracts of cropped land plus livestock (Cheng *et al*, 2022). Food insecurity issues have been on the rise among most citizens, yet water bodies have been greatly threatened by these calamities, resulting in reduced availability of clean portable precious minerals. Frequent droughts have brought devastating effects in Zimbabwe during the years 1982, 2002, 2007, 2012, 2020, to mention a few (Prajapat *et al*, 2024). The Chimanimani cyclone Itai flood disaster, which took away humans and livestock, bears the true living testimony for the need to establish robust, resilient agricultural strategies to safeguard the lives of both human beings, crops, and livestock at large. Tertiary institutions are faced with water shortages, boreholes running dry, crops and livestock programs being faced with increased pests and disease incidences thus leading to reduced agricultural food productivity. These negative effects have not spared the local farming communities, and the general populace in Zimbabwe.

AIMS OF THE STUDY

To identify the impact of climate change in agricultural systems, challenges faced by tertiary institutions, identify resilient agricultural practices, and further prescribe the way forward for policy recommendations in institutions of higher learning and to the local farming communities.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

What are the resilient agricultural practices currently embraced by institutions of higher and tertiary education?

Which challenges are faced by tertiary institutions in the pursuit of adopting resilient agricultural practices?

How can tertiary institutions strategies on resilient agricultural practices in order to improve agricultural productivity and food security systems?

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

To identify various resilient agricultural practices that institutions of higher and tertiary education are currently using to embrace climate change.

To identify challenges faced by tertiary institutions in the pursuit of adopting resilient agricultural practices for food productivity and sustenance.

To prescribe strategies on resilient agricultural practices that can be adopted by institutions of higher and tertiary education to improve their agricultural productivity and food security systems.

To generate knowledge on climate-smart smart resilient agricultural practices for use in future research studies.

METHODOLOGY

The study on resilient agriculture systems employed a multi-methodological approach, which incorporated questionnaires and observational methods. Both qualitative and quantitative methods of data collection were used. An extensive review of literature was conducted to investigate agricultural livelihoods, climate change impacts on agriculture, and the various climate resilience adaptation strategies being implemented elsewhere. Sampling was purposive and followed a stratified sampling technique. Questionnaires were administered in persons to the respondents, who included the agricultural lecturers at one secondary teacher training college, lecturers from one agricultural training college, and a few agricultural business advisors within the Umguza and Umzingwane districts. To minimize bias in data collection, a pre-mapping of the study area and pretesting of the questionnaire (pilot-tested with 2 lecturers and 2 agricultural business advisors) was done. The questionnaire consisted of a structured set of open-ended and closed-ended questions designed to elicit specific information regarding climate change impacts and adaptation strategies

from respondents. On quantitative designs, statistical analysis was done where data collected using questionnaires were counted and analysed.

FINDINGS AND OBSERVATIONS

The study established that 70 % of respondents view the adoption of resilient agricultural practices being key to agricultural productivity and sustenance in the face of climate change. About 80 % of respondents confirm having adopted part of resilient agricultural practices within the tertiary institutions, but strongly feel that institutions haven't done enough to match the call. Most respondents agreed on the negative impacts on food shortages, increased food prices, altered seasons, increased livestock death, and increased pests and disease incidences as being driven by climatic changes. The study unearthed that though some tertiary institutions had adopted practices that include Pfumvudza/Intwasa, drought-tolerant crops, diversification, and early planting to a certain level, they still lag in water harvesting technologies, green housing practices, drip irrigation methodologies, agroforestry practices, and in small stock production and management, Fig. 1. Some respondents cited that limited land for diverse entrepreneurial activities remains a hurdle in their efforts to become food secure. A plethora of challenges face institutions that include a lack of mechanisation, a lack of water harvesting facilities, a lack of capital, diverse preferences by administrators on investments, bureaucratic procurement systems, and restrictive policy environments.

Figure 1: Resilient practices practiced by tertiary institutions

CONCLUSION

The study established that adoption of resilient agricultural practices being key to agricultural productivity and sustenance. Most tertiary institutions haven't done enough in embracing climate resilient agricultural practices and as a result are still harshly influenced by climatic changes which has lead to their over dependence on other institutions for some of their agricultural related food products, a sign of food insecurity. Some efforts have been made on partially adopting such practices as Pfumvudza/Intwasa, growing of drought-tolerant crops, diversification into different croing enterprises, and the practicing of early planting to a certain level, however results revealed that most of them lag behind on establishing improved water harvesting systems, investing fully in green house technologies, establishing full drip irrigation systems among the most notable ones. Research has shown that lack of capital due to financial climate, bureaucratic procurement systems, restrictive policy environments, lack of mechanisation programmes earmarked for tertiary institutions, and diverse preferences by administrators has been among the key notable causes to the current state of affairs in tertiary institutions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The researcher recommends that institutions of tertiary education ought to consider adopting the use of fully fledged greenhouses, precision agricultural practices, improve on water harvesting technologies, and invest in drip irrigation systems. The practice of keeping drought-tolerant small stock livestock such as Kalahari and Matebele goats in drought-stricken regions, commercialization of agriculture through use of public/private partnerships, and embarking on robust entrepreneurial training programs for both lecturers and students are most of the most recommended approaches in the face of the current climate dilemma. Recommendations are in line with Mango *et al*, (2025), who recommended the adoption of improved water harvesting and storage techniques, use of

efficient irrigation schemes, cultivation of drought-tolerant crops such as sorghum and millets for drought-prone regions, and adhering to early warning systems. The authors further argue that diversification of on-farm income sources, practicing proper livestock management, and engaging in farmer training practices are ideal in mitigating the negative impacts of climate change on agriculture. Conclusively, tertiary institutions with limited agricultural land are urged to secure more land for embarking on some of these sustainable agricultural enterprises for their social emancipation and economic development. Further research on some of the constraints in adopting resilient agriculture in these tertiary institutions will go a long way in the development of these academic institutions.

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